

Retarded Time and Radiation from an Accelerated Charge Part II

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In this note, we wish to try to examine radiation from an accelerating charge in a global manner and then move towards the ideas of retarded time. It is known that Maxwell's equations imply that the presence of electric E and magnetic B fields and in turn that there exists an energy density $c^2 E \cdot E + c^2 B \cdot B$. According to Einstein $E = mc^2$, so we argue that if the core charge (where almost all of the rest mass exists) accelerates, so too must the em energy density. This implies that E must change according to acceleration. The E field, however, follows from $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \dot{A}$, where ϕ and A are the electrostatic and magnetic vector potentials. Given a charge at rest, this same charge may be viewed from a frame moving at a constant speed and be seen to have electric and magnetic fields. The question is whether the E field of the rest charge is completely coupled to the charge. (It is already known that it is not in the acceleration case, but we argue that there are a variety of constraints involved in the moving problem and these lead to decoupling of some electromagnetic energy density from the charge system.)

If one considers the $-\text{grad } \phi$ term of E , grad should act on $1/r$ terms to create an E associated with the charge(s). An extra constraint on pieces of the charge density could also be r dependent and lead to an r presence in the numerator of ϕ . In such a case, grad would not necessarily act on the denominator only and there could be em energy density which decouples from the charged system due to this constraint. (Similar arguments hold for all terms of E and B .)

We try to link this feature to asynchronous time signals which we called independent degrees of freedom in Part I. These independent degrees of freedom are constrained to act according to acceleration in a manner independent of the core charge. The constraint is that all charge pieces must deliver a signal (which can only travel at speed c) to the measurement point at the same time t . Thus, on the one hand, one has a collective system, but on the other hand the measurement sees asynchronous effects.

Two kinds of independent acceleration occur and the system is broken into a collective core piece with fast dropping fields and a piece of electromagnetic energy which accelerates, but is no longer part of the charge system because changes are due to the signal constraint. This second piece becomes radiated photons because two collective acceleration constraints are applied, one to the charge core and one to the em energy density. There is nothing in the electromagnetic equation constraining these two energy pieces from being joined like two masses joined by spring or rigid bar.

Thus, the retarded time constraint and Maxwell's em equations are not completely compatible in holding all of the em energy density together if a charge accelerates.

Argument for Acceleration of Two "Masses"

If one has a charge (or charge distribution), it is assumed to have rest mass as well. It may be accelerated and this should have consequences on the E and B fields (electric and magnetic fields) given by Maxwell's em equations.

We note that from Maxwell's equations it is possible to show that:

$$\text{Energy density} = \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + 1/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad ((1))$$

According to Einstein $E = mc^2$, so there are two masses in the accelerating system, the rest mass of the charges and the electromagnetic mass. The latter is usually a tiny value, nevertheless it exists. As a result, the acceleration of the charge system should change the kinetic energy of the charges as well as the em energy. This implies that \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} must change in a manner associated with the acceleration, i.e. according to a collective parameter, namely acceleration.

The question which arise is: Do Maxwell's equations allow for the acceleration of the core mass and the electromagnetic energy (mass) density to accelerate completely together? We argue that the answer is no and investigate this further.

Electrostatic and Magnetic Vector Potentials

It may be argued that an electrostatic potential ϕ and a vector magnetic potential \mathbf{A} exist on mathematical grounds by examining Maxwell's em equations. The relationships are:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad } \phi - d\mathbf{A}/dt \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B} = \text{grad } \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((2b))$$

We focus on the $\text{grad } \phi$ by itself for the moment. In the electrostatic case of a charge at rest, $\phi = q/r$, so grad acts on an r in the denominator changing it to $1/r^2$, i.e. \mathbf{E} drops off with r faster than ϕ . \mathbf{E} is associated with force on another charge q_1 , through $q_1 \mathbf{E}$, but is also linked with self-energy density through $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$. (Focusing on other terms in ((2a)) and ((2b)) does not change our conclusions.)

If one has acceleration of the charge, then grad acting on $1/r$ type terms acceleration, describes the \mathbf{E} field "bound" to the charge system. The em energy density, however, may also accelerate without necessarily being coupled to the charge, so there should be a changed \mathbf{E} piece due to acceleration with r 's in the denominator left untouched. We note that this is a collective effect as one uses the collective parameter acceleration. The question is: How does grad lead to a term proportional to acceleration or even linked to acceleration without touching r in the denominator of ϕ ? (One might argue that one should consider other terms in ((2a)) and ((2b)) and not simply $\text{grad } \phi$, but we argue that the relevant physics is present in $\text{grad } \phi$. One may later examine all terms in ((2a)) and ((2b)).)

To examine this, we consider definitions for ϕ and \mathbf{A} , first without the notion of retarded time. We use (1) (except that (1) includes retarded time which we will later discuss.)

First, consider a fixed origin and a fixed measurement point \mathbf{r} vector at time t . Next, consider a piece of charge at \mathbf{r}' vector at time t . If the effects of this piece of charge could be field instantaneously at \mathbf{r} vector, t , then:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}, t) = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \int dv' \text{ charge density}(\mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}, t) \quad dv' / R \quad ((3a))$$

where $R = | \mathbf{r} \text{ vector} - \mathbf{r}' \text{ vector} |$ ((3b))

Similarly: $A(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}, t) = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \int \frac{dv' J(\mathbf{r}' \text{ vector}, t')}{R}$ ((3c))

In the case of ϕ and the grad operator there is no notion of v in the numerator, although it is present in the denominator because for \mathbf{r}' vector lying along the x axis and \mathbf{r} vector also along the x axis and velocity along the x axis:

$\mathbf{r}' \text{ vector} = \mathbf{r}_0 + \mathbf{v}t$ ((5))

The point we wish to make is that given ((3a)), there is no sense of velocity or acceleration in the numerator of ϕ (or A for that matter).

A second assumption, or constraint, however which introduces the idea of independent degrees of freedom in what seems to be a completely collective charge-field system can introduce the sense of velocity/acceleration in the numerator and leading to decoupling of some em energy density.

This seems to be where the notion of retarded time enters. In ((2a)) and ((2c)), each charge piece at corresponding \mathbf{r}' vectors is able to affect \mathbf{r} vector at the same time t , even though $R = | \mathbf{r} \text{ vector} - \mathbf{r}' \text{ vector} |$ differs for each. Thus, a signal is sent with a fast speed if R is large and a slow speed if R is small, if the E field does not simply appear instantaneously. One may ask: How can the signal coming from a charge piece "know" the distance R ? Thus, it seems more reasonable that a constant speed exists which is set at c and holds in all frames of reference. This means that signals must be sent at different times, i.e. retarded times, depending on the length of R . In other words, t in ((2a)) and ((2c)) should become:

t in charge density and current density $\rightarrow t - R/c$ ((6))

Now \mathbf{r}' contains $\mathbf{v}t$, so velocity exists in the numerator of ((2a)) and a derivative acting on it may create an acceleration term without touching \mathbf{r} in the denominator, hence decoupling a piece of the E field (and thus a piece of em energy density) from the charged system.

As a result, one has many degrees of freedom or signals from different pieces of charge, but these are all constrained in the sense that their signals must arrive at the measurement point at the same t . Furthermore, $\mathbf{r}'(i) \text{ vector} = \mathbf{r}'(i) + \mathbf{v}t$. Thus, there is a collective feature to these signals as well.

The presence of retarded time changes ((2a)) and ((2c)) and the corresponding E and B field calculations. It is now possible to have changes in E due to the numerator containing $t - R/c$, but such changes do not affect \mathbf{r} in the denominator, which is the E linked to a charge system. Thus, it seems that two independent accelerated energies are emerging, the core charge with fast dropping fields and the electromagnetic density with grad not acting on \mathbf{r} in the denominator. These have different \mathbf{r} in the denominator dependence as will be seen.

We follow (1) (page 458-459).

First: $R \approx = r - r' \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} / r$ ((6a))

Second: $1 / (r - r' \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} / r) \approx \text{equal } 1/r + 1/(rr) r' \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} / r$
....((6b))

Third: $\text{density}(r', t-r/c + r' \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} / (cr) = \text{density}(r' \text{ vector}, t-r/c) + r' \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} / (cr) * \text{density}/dt$ (at $r' \text{ vector}, t-r/c$) ((6c))

This leads to: $\phi(r \text{ vector}, t) = 1 / (4 * 3.14 \text{ eo}) \{ q/r + r \text{ vector dot } p(t-r.c) / (rrr) + r \text{ vector dot } dp/dt (t-r/c) / (crr) + \dots$ ((7))

Here p is the dipole moment. For a single charge moving in the x direction, $p = q r'$ and $dp/dt = q v$.

Thus, the collective parameter v emerges, but if there is no acceleration, $\text{grad } \phi$ will only act on r terms in the denominator, i.e. r terms linked to the charge in the usual manner. If acceleration is present, one must have collective acceleration appear for the em energy density and it does through:

$$d/dr dp/dt (t-r/c) = -1/c d/dt dp/dt \quad ((8))$$

For a charge moving in the x direction: $d/dt dp/dt = q \text{ acceleration}$ ((9))

Thus, $\text{grad } \phi$ yields a term proportional to the collective acceleration with the r in the denominator remaining untouched. It is argued that this describes acceleration of part of the electromagnetic energy density, but that this is disconnected from the electromagnetic energy which remains part of the charge system and drops as one higher power of r in the denominator (i.e. Grad acts on r in the denominator). The accelerating charge system has become decoupled because there is electromagnetic energy which must accelerate (change its E) without changing r in the denominator. One has two energy systems and the decoupled em energy density moves off as photons.

In other words, there is nothing in Maxwell's em equations which forces all em energy density to remain coupled to the charge system if the constraint of retarded time is presence. The two constraints (em equations and retarded time) are not completely compatible in keeping all of the E, B fields bound to the charge system.

Discussion in Terms of Degrees of Freedom

We argued that introducing retarded time means each piece of charge sends a signal at its own unique time. We thus argue that single degrees of freedom emerge. These, however, are constrained by the collective velocity and acceleration of the core charge system as well as the retarded time constraint. If one only has constant velocity, then given that one may go into a rest frame, the whole system seems to be one. In the case of acceleration, there are two collective parameters, velocity(t) and acceleration and two sets of accelerated masses, namely the core

charges and em energy density. The question is whether all of the em energy density may remain attached to the core charges. The arguments of (1) show that this cannot be as the constraint due to retarded time allows for grad phi to act on charge density in the numerator of phi and not r in the denominator. Grad must act on the denominator for E fields linked to the charge. Thus, the collective constraint in the retarded time leads to the breaking of an accelerated charge system into two energy parts, the core and fields for which grad acts on r in the denominator and a part for which grad acts on the charge density. (There are also considerations associated with A, but these do not change this conclusion.)

In other words, it seems to be that one may argue that electromagnetic energy is not completely coupled to the core charges as two masses might be coupled by a spring or a rod. This partial couple allows for independence in accelerating the charge plus fast dropping field pieces and another set of less fast dropping pieces associated with retarded time (linked to many degrees of freedom).

Conclusion

A charge system at rest has an E field which drops as $1/(r^2)$ and a self energy $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$. Thus, one does not only have the rest mass of the charge, but em energy density. If one accelerates the rest mass (which is the overwhelming portion of mass), there is no a priori reason that the em energy is coupled in such a way that it accelerates and remains part of the charge. There is no spring or rod joining them as in the case of two masses. Certainly, a moving charge can still have E and B fields because one may view the rest charge from a constantly moving frame. Not all of the em density, however, may remain coupled if one accelerates the charge, especially if constraints in addition to Maxwell's equations exist.

In order to investigate whether some em density may leave, it seems that if this is the case, this density, linked to $.5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + 1/\mu_0 B \cdot B$, must have changed E and B fields such that r terms in the denominator of phi and A do not get acted upon by derivatives used to calculate E and B. We consider only the -grad phi piece, but all pieces lead to the same conclusion. In order that grad phi not touch the denominator, there must be an r present in the numerator and this must come from the charge density. This leads to the idea of a constraint (linked with r) appearing in the numerator. We suggest that this constraint is retarded time (which has been discussed above.) Thus, many signals (degrees of freedom) are constrained to deliver a signal at the same time t to a measurement point. The retarded time leads to terms proportional to $p(t-r/c)$ and $dp/dt(t-r/c)$ where $p = \text{dipole moment} = q r'$ for a single charge moving in the x axis with $r' = r_0 + vt$. Thus, grad may act on the dipole moment and its time derivative. Acting on the time derivative brings in a second time derivative or acceleration value. Collective acceleration linked with retarded time (i.e. many degrees of freedom) leads to grad acting on the numerator and not denominator of phi and decouples the charge puls fields with grad acting on r in the denominator from fields with grad acting on the numerator.

As a result, the decoupled system becomes an accelerating charge with its field and a second partial em energy density piece representing radiated photons.

In short, the constraint of retarded time allows for some E and B pieces to decouple from the accelerating charge system. We note that retarded time is a constraint put in by hand.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wesley 1980)